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GEOG6038 CALIBRATION AND VALIDATION OF EARTH OBSERVATION DATA

Practical M2: Atmospheric Correction of a CASI Image

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Report

“The Role of Ground Targets in Atmospheric Correction of EO Data”

Empirical atmospheric correction techniques, like EML or RELM methods, use measurements of reflectance on the ground using ground targets. The purpose of the ground targets atmospheric correction of Earth observation data is to set a clear, single, well-characterised targets that will serve as model, standard examples of these types of Earth surface. The ground targets are stable, unchanging temporarily and spectrally flat, that's why they are important for the atmospheric correction of the airborne images. The uniform special-temporal stability of the GCP's is necessary for the calibration and atmospheric correction of the EO data. Provision of spectral ground target data for the image classification is therefore a technique which is widely used in radiometric calibration and quantitative analysis (Rollin et al). The target size is related to the sensor spatial resolution, radiometric quality and also to other site-specific factors such as atmospheric conditions and the contrasting reflectance of surrounding surfaces (Moran *et al*, 2001).

Our place of interest is located on the Thorney Island, in West Sussex UK, and the work has been done using ENVI software. The area includes square of concrete (southern part), part of asphalt road, grass-plot and area of water in the south-west of the image. All these types of the ground surface were chosen as ground targets. Making a direct comparison of radiance to a well-defined target (e.g. asphalt, concrete, grass, pebble) with the radiance measured simultaneously enables to evaluate the difference between them and the precision of the measurement. The most uniform and characteristic targets at our image are asphalt

Fig.1. Thorney Island Calibration Site identifying the calibration targets (asphalt, concrete, grass). Image from Rollin *et al*

Fig.2. The CASI data from Thorney Island, 24 July 2001. Acquired at 3109 metres above sea level; nominal pixel size of 4 metres. © NERC, 2001.

(dark surface with low albedo) and concrete (bright surface with high albedo), so that we used them as two main ground targets. We also tried additional surfaces (grass, water and pebble).

The aim of the radiometric calibration is to transform the sensor response from digital number to the units of spectral radiance, to make the measurements independent from the sensor (Rollin *et al*, p.1). While trying two methods of radiometric two methods of the atmospheric correction were used - empirical line methods (ELM) and refine empirical line (RELM). Studying CASI Image (Compact Airborne Spectrographic Imager) we used ground targets in both of these methods. Radiometric calibration for the airborne hyperspectral im-

Fig.3. Setting a spectral ground target (asphalt) in ENVI software

ages is made in several intervals, and the most effective method for the airborne system is using calibration and validation (cal-val) procedures which ensures the accuracy of the measurements. This method includes providing ground data for the image classification and for empirical atmosphere scene correction (Rollin *et al*). The ground target data for the vicarious calibration can be artificial or natural.

The ELM-method is based on the assumption that in every image we can distinguish ground targets of high and low reflectance. The accuracy of the research is increasing with the including of both bright and dark targets in the research (up to 10%), while when using only one target the accuracy can be at about 15-20% (Moran *et al*, 2001). Comparing to ELM-method, the RELM-method includes some refinements and improvements of the ELM, and also includes the RTM

Fig. 4. Spectral Library Viewer: spectrum of asphalt, concrete and zero reflectance in ENVI.

approach for converting radiance of ground targets to the surface reflectance (Moran *et al*, 2001). While using the RELM-method we took in the account the difference between the digital numbers and the

Fig. 5. CASI-asphalt and CASI-concrete spectral profiles in ENVI.

Fig.6. Empirical Line Atmospheric Correction.

value based on two factors: “single high-reflectance target within the scene and an estimate of the image digital number that would be associated with a surface” (Moran *et al*, 2001, p.3).

The work that was made during the Practical 2 aims the atmospheric correction of the Thorney Island and consists of the following steps. First of all, we defined and set places for the ground targets (asphalt and concrete). Then the spectral profiles of our targets were drawn and we compared them; concrete has higher spectral reflectance than that of asphalt (Fig.5). In both profiles the oxygen absorption can be easily seen in the NIR and visible part of spectrum, because the remotely sensed signal measured by airborne sensors in the visible and near infra-red (NIR) is affected by the Earth's atmosphere (Anderson *et al*). Then the spectral library was re-sampled using the TI2003 file. At the next step we were performing the Empirical Line Atmospheric Correction while matching the pairs of the ground target from Data Spectra and Field Spectra (Fig.6). During this step the programme uses the ground targets as model example and matches the ones received during the research.

Fig.7. Performing the Empirical Line Atmospheric Correction

performing the Empirical Line Atmospheric Correction while matching the pairs of the ground target from Data Spectra and Field Spectra (Fig.6). During this step the programme uses the ground targets as model example and matches the ones received during the research.

Fig.8. Difference between original and RELM-corrected spectral profiles in images (right), asphalt

Fig.9. Difference between original and ELM-corrected spectral profiles in images (right), asphalt

For the estimation of uncertainty in reflectance the coefficient of variation is estimated, using the analysis of sequence. Calibration surface reflectance factors is unstable over the time period, so that it can be the reason for the uncertainty (Anderson *et al*).

Fig.10. Difference between original image and RELM-corrected (right), concrete

Fig.11. Difference between original and ELM-corrected spectral profiles (right) in images, concrete

When finally examining the results, received after the image correction using ground targets was done, it becomes clear on the spectrum images that spectrum of all ground targets has been changed to better (Fig. 5-6, 8-9), but the RELM-method is a little more precise and corrected, when carefully comparing the images. Comparing to the model tests enables to analyse whether some parts of the site differ significantly from the average and therefore should be avoided in the analysis (Teillet *et al.*, p.14).

In the future Earth observation sensors will probably be better equipped with instruments and sensors of new technology, but nowadays it is necessary to use calibration and atmospheric correction for the atmospheric correction images. Calibrated hyperspectral images contain measurements of the properties of a surface target and the atmospheric layers between the surface target and the sensor, and therefore the atmospheric correction is necessary, because satellite sensors are still susceptible to atmospheric conditions and the data can be not quite accurate (Sanders *et al.*).

The ground data are important key element in the techniques of the atmospheric correction both in ELM and in RELM methods for accurate results in image interpretation, because the empirical line method for the atmospheric correction is only possible when calibration ground target are available. Important is to choose targets ranged from dark reflectance targets (like asphalt) until those having bright reflective (e.g. concrete, sand, or light soils).

Using correctly chosen ground targets allows to receive highly satisfactory results in the atmospheric correction process of the EO data.

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